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Title:

Philosophical Analysis of Sincerity and Openness in the Perspective of Ludwig Wittgenstein

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This paper presents a philosophical Analysis of Sincerity and Openness through the lens of Ludwig Wittgenstein's philosophy, explicitly applying a convergent argument design. The researcher explores how Wittgenstein's concept of language game illuminates these variables within the concept of individual consultation. By examining key texts, he argues that sincerity transcends personal virtue, emerging as a rational quality shaped by linguistic practices. Openness is framed as a critical engagement that fosters genuine interaction in counseling. The analysis reveals that, according to Wittgenstein, the meaning of Sincerity and Openness is not fixed but contingent on the context of communication. This philosophical manner distinguishes itself as a psychological approach, focusing on the complex dynamics of language and meaning. To conclude, integrating Wittgenstein's notions into counseling can improve our understanding of these concepts, enriching both proactive counseling and seminarian-counselor relationships.

Keywords: *Ludwig Wittgenstein; Philosophy of Language; Philosophical Investigations; Openness; Seminary Formation*

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**Philosophical Analysis of Sincerity and Openness
in the Perspective of Ludwig Wittgenstein**

**Presented to the Instructor of Philosophical Synthesis 2
in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements of the Course Bachelor of Arts in Philosophy of
San Isidro College**

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a philosophical Analysis of Sincerity and Openness through the lens of Ludwig Wittgenstein's philosophy, explicitly applying a convergent argument design. The researcher explores how Wittgenstein's concept of language game illuminates these variables within the concept of individual consultation. By examining key texts, he argues that sincerity transcends personal virtue, emerging as a rational quality shaped by linguistic practices. Openness is framed as a critical engagement that fosters genuine interaction in counseling. The analysis reveals that, according to Wittgenstein, the meaning of Sincerity and Openness is not fixed but contingent on the context of communication. This philosophical manner distinguishes itself as a psychological approach, focusing on the complex dynamics of language and meaning. To conclude, integrating Wittgenstein's notions into counseling can improve our understanding of these concepts, enriching both proactive counseling and seminarian-counselor relationships.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Abstract	1
CHAPTER I: INTRODUCTION	
Background of the Study	3
Statement of the Problem	4
Objectives of the Study	5
Argument Design	5
Significance of the Study	7
Scopes and Delimitation	8
Definition of Terms	9
Thesis Statement	10
CHAPTER II: REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE	
Understanding language	11
Seminary Human Formation	13
Individual Consultation in Seminary Formation	16
Sincerity and Openness in Language	18
Marshall B. Rosenberg, PhD	19
Carl Roger, PhD	22
Ludwig Wittgenstein and Theory of Language	26
1.1 Language game	26
1.2 Language Action	31

1.3 Family Resemblance	32
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CHAPTER III: METHODOLOGY

Research Design	35
Argument Design	35
Presentation of Argument	36

CHAPTER IV: PRESENTATION OF DATA AND DISCUSSION OF ARGUMENTS

Individual Consultation needs Sincerity and Openness to build Trust	37
Context-Dependent Truth and Meaning in Language	40
In the context of language games, asserting	
The truth is like a seminarian hiding their feelings.	43
Truth Parallels sincerity and openness in counseling	46

CHAPTER V: SUMMARY, CONCLUSION, RECOMMENDATION

Summary	50
Conclusion	51
Recommendation	51
Bibliography	54
Abstract	57

Chapter 1

THE PROBLEM

Background of the Study

Communication is a fundamental aspect of human life, with language essential for understanding, connecting, and expressing ideas. Language functions as the mechanism through which individuals communicate meaning in their existence. As stated by Ludwig Wittgenstein, language is an essential tool in communication, acting as a medium for understanding, creating meaning, and fostering connections among people. Likewise, Wittgenstein emphasized language's central role in communication and comprehension. He perceived language as a communication tool and the medium through which people construct and make sense of their world.¹

Within the St. John XXIII College Seminary, communication and conversation are integral to daily routines and contribute significantly to the formation process. These practices foster sincerity and openness through words across all aspects of seminary formation: human, spiritual, pastoral, and academic, thereby enabling deeper relationships among individuals. In addition, communication is essential and is employed in various ways, such as giving recollections, making speeches, and delivering homilies. This communication serves as an instrument for meaningful interaction. On the other hand, individual consultation (I.C.) involves communication between the seminarian and the counselor in human formation. This communication requires the seminarian to

¹ Wittgenstein, Ludwig, "Philosophical Investigations", trans. By G. E. M. Anscombe, et.al., Wiley-Blackwell, 2009, accessed April 15, 2024, <https://static1.squarespace.com/static/54889e73e4b0a2c1f9891289/t/564b61a4e4b04eca59c4d232/1447780772744/Ludwig.Wittgenstein.-.Philosophical.Investigations.pdf>.

use language truthfully, with sincerity and openness, to guide him in his journey and facilitate meaningful interaction.

However, the use of language in private must be considered. There are various ways to express words depending on the context or situation. Conflicts often arise in everyday language use due to the tendency to manipulate information. Individuals shape their words to fit different contexts. The practice frequently results in a lack of openness and sincerity in communication, leading to a loss of language's true essence and meaning in individual lives.

Furthermore, Wittgenstein's theory of meaning highlighted the concepts of language games, where communication follows regular patterns determined by the users, shaping understanding and interpretation. According to Wittgenstein, every language embodies truth, with sincerity and openness as integral aspects of truthful language.

This paper aimed to analyze Ludwig Wittgenstein's theory of language, which underscores the truth of language. The study also explored the potential application of language games in individual consultation (I.C.), considering the importance of sincerity and openness in communication.

Statement of the Problem

This study explores the possibility of sincerity and openness during seminarians' consultations using the language theory (Language game) of Ludwig Wittgenstein.

1. What do sincerity and openness mean in Individual Consultation?
2. What is Wittgenstein's concept of a Language game?
3. How can Wittgenstein's language game improve sincerity and openness in Individual consultation?

Objectives of the Study

The study delves into the concept of individual consultation in seminary formation to understand Ludwig Wittgenstein's theory of language games. Similarly, the researcher analyzes the concepts of sincerity and openness in Ludwig Wittgenstein's theory of language. Specifically, the study has the following objectives.

1. Emphasize sincerity and openness in seminary formation.
2. Understanding Ludwig Wittgenstein's Theory of language, particularly the language game and
3. Analyze the possibility of Ludwig Wittgenstein's theory of language as an effective context for fostering sincerity and openness in individual consultation in seminary formation.

Argument Design

Convergent arguments occur when different lines of reasoning are used to reach the same conclusion. Each reason independently supports the conclusion, even if one reason alone might not be substantial. In this type of argument, the strength derives from the combination of all the reasons. Convergent arguments rely on multiple pieces of evidence or reasoning, all converging to support the same conclusion.²

² Hahn, Ulrike, and Mike Oaksford, "The Rationality of Informal Argumentation: A Bayesian Approach to Reasoning Fallacies," *Psychological Review* 114, no. 3 (2007): 704–732, <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-295X.114.3.704>.

Figure1: Convergent Argument Figure

First, the claim will be based on Wittgenstein's theory of language, incorporating key concepts from the philosopher and specific words supporting the argument.

Second, the researcher will apply these concepts to the counseling process within seminary formation, specifically focusing on human formation. This approach will highlight, explore, and apply Wittgenstein's ideas to strengthen the claims.

Lastly, the resolution gains support from multiple notions and claims, none of which would be adequate independently. However, together, they provide sufficient support. Individually, these claims may lack strength, but collectively, they effectively reinforce the resolution.

Significance of the study

The study acknowledged the philosophical issues surrounding sincerity and openness, particularly the gap between what we do and speak. It emphasizes the importance of being genuine and staying true to beliefs to address these challenges and align theoretical concepts with practical actions. This approach contributes to various aspects of an individual's life:

1. Addressing the Virtue of Sincerity and Openness - the study focused on the key virtues of sincerity and openness, which are central values stipulated at the St. John XXIII College Seminary. The study examined how these virtues shape the behavior and righteousness of seminarians, highlighting their importance in the formation process to become priests. By exploring their role in seminary life, the study aims to reveal how these virtues influence the character and readiness of future priests.

2. In St. John XXIII Seminary - acknowledging the importance of sincerity and openness is imperative for the seminarians, such that it fosters their holistic development and equips them to become effective leaders in the community.

3. Wisdom to Counselor - through this synthesis, the research aims to offer practical insights for formators and counselors, particularly in individual consultations, to foster genuine interaction and conversational values. The findings from this exploration serve as valuable guidance for enhancing seminary formation.

4. The Field of Philosophy - The study recognizes the philosophical challenge of understanding truth today, especially the divide between what we say and do. It addresses this gap by emphasizing the importance of being genuine, transparent, and authentic. Doing so aims to bridge the complexities of truth, bringing together theoretical ideas and real-world actions.

Scope and Delimitation

Firstly, this paper focused specifically on Ludwig Wittgenstein's philosophy of language and the application to the concept of sincerity and openness within individual consultation (I.C.) in seminary formation. The paper does not delve into other aspects of Wittgenstein's philosophical framework, such as in ethics, epistemology, or metaphysics.

Secondly, this paper does not seek to alter Wittgenstein's ideas but rather to explore how his concept of language, particularly regarding sincerity and openness, can be incorporated into individual consultation in seminary formation. The focus is on integrating Wittgenstein's notions of language into the practices and human formation at St. John XXIII College Seminary. Different formation institutions and seminaries may adopt various methods to promote sincerity and openness among individuals. Consequently, the conclusions of this research may only be directly applicable in the context of St. John XXIII Seminary or to other educational settings and seminaries.

Lastly, the researcher selects contemporary books and philosophers, focusing on Ludwig Wittgenstein, to discuss sincerity and openness in the context of individual consultation. The paper explores how these concepts apply to counseling, ensuring the use of trustworthy online sources to support and strengthen the arguments and findings. This paper is not a psychological study but rather a philosophical examination of the presence of psychology in the formation process.

Definition of Terms

The following terms are defined theoretically and operationally.

1. Individual Consultation- Individual counseling (sometimes called psychotherapy, talk therapy, or treatment) is a process through which clients work one-on-one with a trained mental health clinician in a safe, caring, and confidential environment.³ This study defines it as the interaction between the seminarian and counselor in guiding the priestly formation.
2. Openness is the quality of being willing to consider ideas and opinions that are new or different from one's own.⁴ This paper defines transparency through the use of words in communication and action in interaction.
3. Seminary Rule of Life - These documents guide daily communal living and clarify the behavioral expectations of seminarians pursuing a priestly vocation. The Rule of Life also seeks to balance freedom, responsibility, accountability, activities, and solitude.⁵ The study defines it as the structure guideline followed by seminarians during their formation for the priesthood.
4. Sincerity- It is the quality of being honest and straightforward in attitude and speech; truthfulness.⁶ This study defines it as the genuineness and authenticity of language in communication, which fosters meaningful conversation and interaction.

³ "Individual Counseling," California State University Channel Islands, accessed May 17, 2024, <https://www.csuci.edu/caps/individualcounseling.htm>.

⁴ Cambridge Dictionary. s.v. "Openness to Experience," accessed April 7, 2024.

⁵ "Rule of Life and Seminarian Handbook," Mount St. Mary's Seminary, accessed May 9, 2024, <https://seminary.msmary.edu/priestly-formation/human-formation/index.html>.

⁶ Cambridge Dictionary (2022), s.v. "Sincerity," accessed April 7, 2024.

Thesis Statement:

Ludwig Wittgenstein's language game theory fosters greater sincerity and openness in individual consultation during seminary formation by emphasizing how context-dependent communication practices shape authentic and transparent interaction.

Chapter II

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE AND STUDIES

Understanding language

Language refers to the capacity to learn and utilize intricate communication systems, primarily the human ability. Language encompasses specific instances of systems that facilitate connection with others. Furthermore, language is a distinguishing characteristic between humans and animals, representing one of humanity's most valuable attributes. For philosophers, language serves as a tool for thinking, as thoughts are expressed through language, and it plays a crucial role in interactions with others.

Moreover, the knowledge of languages served as the medium for exchanging ideas and developing economic alliances, interpersonal connections, and cultural bonds. The English language has emerged as a distinctive language in many societies. However, many individuals around the globe remain unfamiliar with it despite its role as a unifying force. Language can be utilized in various modalities, including speaking, listening, reading, and writing. The language complexity varies according to the context in which it is employed by the individual, serving as a means for individuals to establish connections and interact in the real world.

As Crystal David noted in his work, language is a human communication system that involves sounds, gestures, and written symbols to convey meaning. It enables individuals to express thoughts, feelings, and ideas and interact and share information with others. Ferdinand de Saussure, in his seminal work "Course in General Linguistics," introduces the concept of the linguistic sign, highlighting the arbitrary relationship between words (signifiers) and their

meanings (signified). He emphasizes the structural aspects of language and its role in shaping thought and perception.⁷

With that understanding, language requires more than just knowledge of its syntax and semantics. Language involves understanding its usage in the various contexts. Chomsky's assertion that language is a foundational element in shaping human thought, perception, and understanding of the world has significantly impacted various fields. Chomsky argued that language offers a unique insight into the working of the human mind, acting as a catalyst for intricate cognitive processes.⁸

In essence, language is the instrument that an individual uses to communicate and understand the world. This encompasses symbols, rules, and interactions that shaped a person's thoughts and actions. Moreover, language is not merely about verbal expression; it also influences how we perceive and engage with reality.

Given this, language is indispensable for creating meaning in life. It enables us to connect with others, express our emotions and ideas, and construct personal identities. We reflect on our experiences and knowledge through language to make sense of the world. Additionally, language impacts our perspectives, relationships, and comprehension of reality. It is a fundamental connector among individuals, lying at the core of human existence. Therefore, imbued with sincerity and openness language holds the truth and enhances human experiences, providing a meaningful purpose for our existence.

⁷ Ferdinand de Saussure, "Course in General Linguistics," trans. Roy Harris, New York: Columbia University Press, 2011, accessed May 13, 2024, https://warwick.ac.uk/fac/arts/english/currentstudents/undergraduate/modules/fulllist/first/en122/lecturelist2019-20/saussure_course_in_general_linguistics.pdf.

⁸ Noam Chomsky, "Language and Mind", 3rd ed. Cambridge: Massachusetts Institute of Technology, Cambridge University Press, 2002, accessed May 14, 2024, <https://www.ugr.es/~fmanjon/Language%20and%20Mind.pdf>.

However, individuals possess a unique ability to manipulate language. They can play with words to evoke various responses, such as laughter or solemnity, from others. This ability allows for different modes of communication depending on the audience, such as using casual language with friends and adopting formal terminology in professional settings.

Nevertheless, individuals use language to obscure the truth or present narratives to enhance their appeal. How individuals employ language reflects their flexibility and creativity. Language relies on sincerity and openness, fostering genuine connections and discouraging selfishness. Conversely, a lack of sincerity and openness can result in superficial interactions.

Kevin Kurdylo defines the philosophy of language as the study of human language's fundamental characteristics. This includes investigating its origins, usage, the relationship between meaning and truth, and how language is intertwined with human cognition, knowledge, and reality.⁹ Language possesses significant influence and can assist individuals in discovering significance. However, it is worth diminishes when we manipulate words or utilize language.

Let us analyze how individuals construct and negotiate their identities through linguistic practices and how this process intersects with their expressions of sincerity and openness. What implications does this have for self-concept, self-esteem, and social belonging? In Wittgenstein's philosophy, language and behavior explore the relationship between language and behavior. How do language games shape individuals' behavioral responses and decision-making processes? How might behavior patterns reflect or diverge from expressions of sincerity and openness within specific language games?

⁹ K. Kurdylo, "Research guides, Home - Research Guides at University of Wisconsin-Madison," Research Guides University of Wisconsin-Madison, accessed May 14, 2024, <https://researchguides.library.wisc.edu/>.

Seminary Human Formation

In the realm of seminary formation, the comprehensive training of candidates should be directed towards them into true shepherds of souls, following the example of our Lord Jesus Christ, who serves as teacher, priest, and shepherd. All priestly formation must be deeply rooted in the core doctrines of the Catholic faith, as this wisdom underpins the very nature and purpose of the ministerial priesthood. Similarly, both formators and seminarians must continually revisit the fundamental teaching of the faith to gain the unified perspective required to fully achieve the four dimensions of formation: human, pastoral, spiritual, and intellectual. The quest for truth is central to the Christian journey. Throughout the process, seminarians should remain committed to the Word of God and the Magisterium, in line with their minds and hearts with this guiding principle of the formation.

A human formation program should promote freedom, openness, honesty and flexibility, joy and inner peace, generosity and justice, personal maturity, interpersonal skills, common sense, aptitude for ministry, and growth "in moral sensibility and character."¹⁰

Openness means intentionally sharing personal information with others, even if it makes us emotionally vulnerable. It involves exposing our inner world and being open about ourselves. This act of deliberate transparency can leave us vulnerable, where we may be emotionally wounded. However, in the context of priestly formation, it has been recognized that such vulnerability, through honest and transparent communication between seminarians and the formation team, is crucial for a meaningful and successful formation process.¹¹

¹⁰ "Program of Priestly Formation." n.d. <https://www.usccb.org/upload/program-priestly-formation-fifth-edition.pdf>.

¹¹ "On Vulnerability and Self-Disclosure in Priestly Formation." 2017. *Homiletic & Pastoral Review*. November 7, 2017.

On the other hand, the Ratio Fundamentalis underscores that in the formation process, a seminarian must engage in self-discovery and be open to being known by others, maintaining sincerity and openness in his interactions with formators. Effective formation relies heavily on personal mentoring and a receptive attitude toward the guidance of the Holy Spirit.

Transparency paves the way for the healing process that many seminarians require. It is essential to acknowledge that suitability for ordination does not mean we have yet to face difficulties in life. We may have experienced hardships and needed healing and growth through our connection with the Divine Physician. Although the Seminary is not ideal for extensive psychological therapy, it should provide an environment where seminarians can achieve personal integration, find inner healing, and cultivate a sense of wholeness. It is a place that supports seminarians in their journey toward greater self-awareness and maturity.¹² For instance, a seminarian with a troubled past finds support in the Seminary's environment of community and transparency. Through individual consultation and brotherhood discussion, he addresses his emotional wounds and gains greater self-knowledge. This healing process helps him achieve personal integrity and prepares him for effective ministry.

Written from the Seminary Rule of Life, Section 4, on Disciplinary Procedure, seminarians should become accustomed to training their character. They should grow in their strength and spirit and learn human virtues, like sincerity of mind, a constant concern for justice, fidelity to one's promises, refinement in manners, and modest speech coupled with charity. This will make them a living reflection of the humanity of Jesus and a bridge that unites people with God. With that, the Seminary reserves the right to dismiss, at any time of the year, any seminarian for any of the following reasons after due investigation- misconduct, dishonesty, lack of spiritual depth, lack of

¹² "On Vulnerability and Self-Disclosure in Priestly Formation." 2017. Homiletic & Pastoral Review. November 7, 2017.

sincerity, involvement of fraternities, chronic inability, health issues, major offenses, etc.¹³ For example, Kianne, a seminarian, repeatedly displays a lack of sincerity and dishonesty, failing to uphold the virtues expected by the seminary. Despite efforts to correct his behavior, his actions undermine the community's trust. After due investigation and observation, the Seminary dismisses him to maintain the integrity of its formation process.

Establishing trust within a seminary depends on maintaining open and honest communication. Trust is crucial for energizing and engaging the community and for enabling effective organizational changes. When transparency and truthfulness are prioritized, it creates a setting where individuals can focus on their duties without concerns about deceit or misinformation. Honesty serves as a cornerstone for personal happiness, success, and contentment and can lead to unforeseen opportunities and experiences, fostering a more liberated and genuine life.

However, honesty involves more than just speaking the truth. It requires being authentic with oneself and others regarding one's true identity, goals, and needs. To live genuinely means to embrace openness in all interactions, which builds credibility and trustworthiness. By being honest, individuals enhance their relationships, strengthen community bonds, and nurture a culture of respect and integrity.

Individual consultation in Seminary formation

Rapid societal changes, shifting cultural norms, and evolving communication methods may breed skepticism and uncertainty in interpersonal connections, making it increasingly difficult for

¹³ St. John XXIII College Seminary Rule of Life. Saint John XXIII College Seminary, Pal -ing, Patpat, Malaybalay City. Updated 2021

individuals to trust others. Consequently, the role of counselors in this era becomes crucial, given their expertise in aiding individuals in their personal growth and navigating various challenges throughout their life journeys.

Counseling encompasses many theoretical frameworks and practical strategies for helping individuals or groups examine and resolve their issues. Counselors utilize various methodologies to incorporate logical reasoning, aiming for a deeper understanding and purposeful discourse.

This course focuses on understanding and implementing various counseling theories and approaches within therapeutic settings. It considers contemporary topics such as technology-supported treatment and integrating spirituality into counseling practice.¹⁴

In addition, it recognizes the importance of counseling for the current generation of young individuals. Counseling provides a safe space for teenagers to explore their emotions, navigate academic and social challenges, and build resilience in the face of difficulties. By integrating counseling into mental health care, we can foster the well-being of future generations. Recognizing the evolving needs of today's young individual seminary formation integrates counseling as a key component in fostering the will of seminarians. Counseling provides a safe space for seminarians to explore their human, pastoral, intellectual, and spirituality and build resilience. By establishing a proficient counselor-seminarian interaction, trust is developed, personal growth is supported, and profound guidance is offered. Counselors play an important role in enhancing emotional well-being and resilience, facilitating effective communication, and helping the seminarians understand and address the complexities of life. In this manner, seminarians are well-prepared for their future roles both personally and in ministry.

¹⁴ David Capuzzi et.al., "Counseling and Psychotherapy: Theories and Interventions" , American Counseling Association, March 29, 2022, <https://www.amazon.com/Counseling-Psychotherapy-Interventions-David-Capuzzi-ebook/dp/B09WYBT8K5>.

Therefore, while trusting someone can be challenging, counseling can help achieve it. Establishing a proficient interaction is crucial in this process. Counselors play a vital role in building trust, fostering personal development, offering guidance to clients, and facilitating the sharing and enhancing of individuals' experiences. In communication, language plays a crucial role in facilitating understanding and establishing a connection between the client and the seminarian, enabling insights into the intricacies of life. Additionally, counselors assist seminarians in enhancing their emotional well-being and resilience in confronting life's challenges.

Sincerity and Openness in Language

Language serves as the bridge to meaningful conversation and understanding, where it is essential to be true and honest in its use. Moreover, sincerity and openness in communication are crucial for genuine human connection, going beyond mere words. These qualities foster meaningful interactions, serving as the foundation for developing empathy, deepening understanding, and strengthening bonds between people. More so, sincerity in language enables people to communicate openly and honestly, creating a sense of vulnerability that elicits responses and fosters stronger connections. It is important to value these qualities in communication, as losing them can lead to misunderstanding and lack of clarity for the speaker. Hence, there is power in using words authentically, enabling individuals to convey messages sincerely and foster genuine connections.

According to Smith in his book "The Art of Honest Communication," language and sincerity are deeply intertwined aspects of human communication. Sincerity refers to being genuine, honest, and truthful in one's expression, while language serves as the medium through which sincerity is conveyed. When people communicate sincerely, they use language to express

their thoughts, feelings, and intentions. There is power in the use of words to convey sincerity. Individuals need to value this quality to find meaning in their communication. As Sarah Jones stated in "Deceptive Communication: Impact on Trust and Relationships," authenticity fosters trust and understanding in interpersonal relationships. Conversely, insincerity in language, such as deceptive or manipulative speech, can erode trust and lead to misunderstandings.¹⁵

In addition, open conversations are the cornerstones of a great communicator. It allows for raw, honest self-expression and fuels an environment of trust and empathy. Open communication leads to an opportunity for the unlimited exchange of ideas without fear of refusal. In this way, it helps people to express what they think openly about their ideas and emotions as well as concepts related to points of view with others, which, in turn, creates good relationships and mutual exchanges. Open-minded communication allows you to hear, understand, and empathize with other people's experiences. Openness enables us to build strong bonds and a sense of community and deal with difficult situations

together as one unit.

Openness in language involves the capacity and openness to be direct, candid, and transparent when expressing oneself. Real communication leads to confidence and forms relationships. As Danie said, closed language can also lead to misunderstandings. Appreciative openness provides an opportunity for real relationships and authentic connections.

Consequently, the connection between language and denotation boils down to demonstrating human speech, as genuine open-heartedness motivates exchanging living moments with humans.

¹⁵ Sarah Jones, "Deceptive Communication, Impact on Trust and Relationships," Boston: Beacon Press, 2020, 47-60.

Marshall B. Rosenberg, PhD.

Marshall B. Rosenberg, PhD (1934-2015), was a renowned figure known for developing Nonviolent Communication (NVC) training and establishing the Center for Nonviolent Communication. His primary focus was on conflict resolution, where he offered valuable insights and methodologies for peaceful resolution of conflicts. In addition to conflict resolution, Rosenberg's work extended to education reform, where he helped schools and teachers create more nurturing environments through compassionate communication. He aimed to promote understanding, empathy, and constructive dialogue in interpersonal relationships and educational settings.¹⁶

On one hand, "sincerity" originates from the Latin word "sincere," which means clean, sound, or pure. Interestingly, the term first appeared in English during the early 16th century and was initially used to describe inanimate objects. For example, one might have referred to "sincere wine," indicating its unmixed qualities. According to Trilling (1972) and Guilhamet (1974), by the time of Shakespeare, the term was regularly applied to individuals, initially metaphorically and later with the literal meaning of the absence of dissimulation, feigning, or pretense.¹⁷

Additionally, sincerity in language enables individuals to express themselves honestly and authentically. Without hidden motives, this approach fosters genuine connections and trust through passionate communication, strengthening relationships and interactions. Furthermore, individual consultation involves the person seeking advice and the advisor being honest and genuine in

¹⁶ NVCAcademy, "Excellence in online learning since 2006", accessed May 17, 2024, <https://nvcacademy.com/nonviolent-communication/marshall-rosenberg>.

¹⁷ Paul Stenner, Sincerity and Authenticity, A Social Psychological Study of 'Aspirational Models,' (Changes 17, no. 4, 1999), 6.

exchanging ideas and feelings. For the individual seeking assistance, honesty entails openly disclosing issues and goals while remaining receptive to guidance. Similarly, for the advisor, sincerity involves providing well-intentioned advice while avoiding prejudices and focusing solely on the individual's best interests. Mutual honesty cultivates trust and creates an environment conducive to successful communication and problem-solving.

Meanwhile, Dr. Daniel Kahneman emphasizes the importance of trust and rapport in decision-making processes. You are arguing that sincerity is crucial in establishing and maintaining confidence among individuals in consultation scenarios. Therefore, sincere communication fosters a sense of trustworthiness and genuineness, enhancing exchanges' efficiency.¹⁸

In connection with Marshall Rosenberg's notion that misunderstanding often leads to disconnection and conflict, Nonviolent Communication (NVC) offers a pathway to authentic connection, understanding, and peace rooted in sincerity. Through listening and speaking with empathy and honesty, we can transcend barriers, resolve conflicts, and foster relationships built on mutual respect and genuine compassion. In the book "Nonviolent Communication," the author provides a compelling illustration of sustaining a meaningful and genuine conversation: "When we engage in heartfelt giving, we do so with the genuine pleasure that arises when we willingly enhance another individual's life. This type of giving is advantageous for both the donor and the recipient." The recipient enjoys the gift without fear, guilt, humiliation, or a desire for personal advantage.

Meanwhile, the benefactor benefits from a heightened sense of self-worth by witnessing their positive impact on someone's welfare.

¹⁸ Daniel Kahneman, *Thinking, Fast and Slow*, (New York: Farrar, Straus and Giroux, 2011), 123.

Moreover, nonviolent communication does not require the individuals we engage with to possess literacy in NVC or even exhibit a desire to connect with us empathetically. By adhering to the principles of NVC and maintaining a steadfast commitment to compassionate giving and receiving without revealing our underlying motives, one can inspire others to join in this process. Over time, this enables effective and empathetic responses between individuals.¹⁹

Carl R. Rogers, PhD.

Carl R. Rogers (1902–1987) is recognized as one of the pioneers of humanistic psychology. He pioneered clinical psychological research and established the person-centered approach to psychotherapy, sometimes known as a client-centered approach. He also introduced the concept of unconditional positive regard.²⁰ Likewise, communication occurs for a reason. To help avoid misunderstandings and communicate more effectively, individuals must understand the context of the communication.²¹

Being open means being honest, truthful, and willing to discuss difficult things. This is akin to opening a door to better communication, understanding, and meaningful interaction. Exploring the importance of openness in counseling, specifically in an individual consultation, allows individuals to feel safe sharing and growing in their journey according to their purpose.

¹⁹ Marshall B. Rosenberg, *Nonviolent Communication: A Language of Life* (Encinitas, CA: Puddle Dancer Press, 2006), 21.

²⁰ American Psychological Association, "Carl R. Rogers," accessed May 17, 2024, <https://www.apa.org/about/governance/president/carl-r-rogers>.

²¹ Jim Stovall and Ray H. Hull, "The Art of Communication: Your Competitive Edge," Shippensburg, PA: Sound Wisdom, 2016, 28, https://static1.squarespace.com/static/593f2e783e00be3feb4325c7/t/594db6b937c5812dce526577/1498265278600/ArtOfCommunication_PREVIEW.pdf.

Moreover, being open and honest is essential in counseling. When individuals openly share their thoughts and feelings, it helps the counselor understand them better and build trust. This facilitates seminarians' clients' talking about problems, finding solutions, and being guided as individuals in society.

However, openness is vital in individual consultation due to various factors such as trust issues, fear of judgment, and lack of sincerity. In Carl Roger's concept of the person-centered approach, particularly in one of his therapeutic conditions as mentioned in the book "Four Approaches of Counseling and Psychotherapy," it is highlighted that clients who have had experiences with significant people in their lives being dishonest or less than open may find it challenging to believe in someone truthful, honest, and open. Being congruent in a therapeutic relationship can feel risky for the counselor. Moreover, fostering this kind of attitude is challenging for the counselor, as they must first demonstrate the value of openness to their client.

Rogers believed the therapist should have expressed persistent feelings during the session. He argued that clients would sense these feelings anyway, and concealing them would disrupt the therapeutic process. The counselor's outward responses should align with their inner feelings, as congruent triangles match each other precisely in size and shape. Counselors must remain fully aware of their emotions during the session and "live these feelings, be them in the relationship, and communicate them if appropriate" (Rogers 1962, 417).

Various terms have been used interchangeably with congruence, including genuineness, realness, openness, authenticity, and transparency. Each term captures some aspect of this condition. Rogers particularly favored the term "transparent," suggesting that the counselor is so open in the relationship that the client can see right through to the natural person. By genuinely

being themselves, counselors strongly message their clients that being true to their inner selves is acceptable and beneficial.²²

Furthermore, the client learns to trust the counselor, knowing that any responses can be accepted as honest. This trust is earned through the counselor's genuineness in the relationship and is not based on any perceived expertise. By being willing to openly express feelings of confusion, helplessness, irritation, or fallibility, the counselor demonstrates self-acceptance despite these perceived "weaknesses" and sends a powerful message to the client.²³ That makes openness crucial in individual consultation, enabling individuals to deepen their understanding of existence, find meaning in the process, and accept their identity and community.

Moreover, the book *On Becoming a Person: A Therapist's View of Psychotherapy* by Carl Rogers emphasizes the significance of openness in interpersonal communication, especially in the therapeutic context. Rogers demonstrates that genuine openness, characterized by empathetic understanding, unconditional positivity, and authenticity, is essential for establishing and nurturing meaningful interactions among individuals. Openness in therapy partnerships fosters an atmosphere where individuals can freely communicate their emotions and thoughts without fear of criticism, facilitating profound comprehension and personal development. When individuals recognize the importance of being open, they become willing to confront the truth of acceptance and embrace new experiences for personal development.

Additionally, this increased openness to internal processes is linked to a corresponding openness to external reality. When Maslow refers to self-actualized individuals, he may describe clients who possess a remarkable ability to repeatedly and genuinely appreciate the fundamental

²² Windy Dryden and Jill Mytton, *Four Approaches to Counselling and Psychotherapy* (London: Routledge, 1999), 78.

²³ Dryden and Mytton, *Four Approaches to Counselling and Psychotherapy*, 79.

joys of life with a sense of pleasure, wonder, and even ecstasy, even if these experiences seem dull or unexciting to others.²⁴ Furthermore, recognizing the significance of transparency in engaging in a dialogue can help you acknowledge your presence and facilitate a connection with another individual.

TOWARD ACCEPTANCE OF OTHERS

Closely related to this openness to inner and outer experience in general is an openness to and acceptance of other individuals. As a client moves toward being able to accept his own experience, he also moves toward the acceptance of the experience of others. He values and appreciates both his own experience and that of others for what it is. To quote Maslow again regarding his self-actualizing individuals: "One does not complain about water because it is wet nor about rocks because they are hard. . . . As the child looks out upon the world with wide, uncritical, and innocent eyes, simply noting and observing what is the case, without either arguing the matter or demanding that it be otherwise, so does the self-actualizing person look upon human nature both in himself and others."²⁵

Conversely, language plays a significant role in fostering the appreciation of openness. It serves as a tool for communication, allowing receptive individuals to engage with new ideas, express their thoughts, and better understand others. Language facilitates the exchange of novel ideas and the acquisition of knowledge about diverse life circumstances. Additionally, it fosters creativity and enables individuals to adapt to changes by explicitly expressing their ideas. Openness in language can aid in connecting individuals. Wittgenstein's notion of language games encompasses the mechanics of language and its relational nature, including its connections to society, others, and individuals. Language serves as a medium for self-expression and plays a crucial role in interpersonal communication. Language games involve individuals negotiating meaning within specific situations, utilizing shared conventions and understanding. Language is a personal and communal endeavor, requiring individuals to coordinate and reach a consensus.

²⁴ Carl R. Rogers, *On Becoming a Person: A Therapist's View of Psychotherapy*, Peter D. Kramer, M.D. (New York: Houghton Mifflin Harcourt Publishing Company, 1995), 156.

²⁵ Rogers, *On Becoming a Person*, 157.

Furthermore, language functions within interpersonal connections, influencing and being influenced by personal dynamics. It shapes how individuals communicate with each other, impacting the depth of understanding and the quality of relationships.

Ludwig Wittgenstein's Theory of Language

1.1 Language game

Language games are dynamic and molded by diverse social contexts, devoid of fixed meanings. They underscore that language is intricately tied to specific activities or contexts, each governed by its rules and conventions. Understanding language games enables us to grasp the complexity of language and its pivotal role in human interaction, guiding us in communication across various life situations. In Wittgenstein's notion, "language games" refer to concrete social activities that employ particular linguistic forms. Wittgenstein aimed to illustrate that "the act of speaking a language is a component of an activity or a way of life" by showcasing various types of language games and the myriad ways language is utilized in human communication.²⁶

However, it is crucial to recognize that even the words we use are conventional or agreed upon by a specific group. Each word adheres to a rule to enhance its understanding in context, with every rule reflecting and applying to the situation of a particular group. Additionally, we must acknowledge that the term "rules" takes on a distinct meaning from Wittgenstein's concept. Understanding language entails grasping these rules and understanding how they function in different contexts and interactions. Language operates based on rules inherent in its use rather than external imposition.

²⁶ Encyclopedia Britannica. s.v. "Ludwig Wittgenstein," last modified April 25, 2024, accessed May 20, 2024, <https://www.britannica.com/biography/Ludwig-Wittgenstein>.

Moreover, Wittgenstein's exploration of language games, particularly in his later writings, carries significant implications for the theory of signs. These language games encompass various sign-related practices and provide a common conceptual framework that facilitates our comprehension, production, and interpretation of signs. The rules and boundaries inherent in language games enable us to communicate and interpret signs across various situations effectively.²⁷ In other words, language-game analysis enables us to understand that language operates like a game, comprising actions (behavior) and rules (grammar) that we can utilize appropriately and effectively for specific purposes. Language is inherently dynamic, and each word in a language carries meaning. However, simply using words only conveys meaningful information if we explain the distinction we intend to establish.²⁸

The language-game proposition suggests that language is not static or rigid but dynamic and flexible. Words' meaning is not determined by some universal truth or definition but rather by how they are utilized in specific contexts or "games" of language. Like games where rules and situations can vary, words and language acquire significance through application and use in different contexts.

Moreover, language plays a vital role in communication. Jurgen Habermas emphasizes the crucial role of language as the medium for rational communication in forming societal consensus and the functioning of the public sphere. Habermas built upon Wittgenstein's notion of language games, focusing on how language is a tool for achieving mutual understanding and consensus in social interactions. Habermas argues that effective discourse is free from domination and coercion,

²⁷ "Ludwig Wittgenstein: Language Games / Signo - Applied Semiotics Theories." n.d., last modified February 15, 2013, May 20, 2024, Wwww.signosemio.com. <http://www.signosemio.com/wittgenstein/language-games.asp>.

²⁸ Ludwig Wittgenstein, G. Anscombe, and Basil Blackwell, *Philosophical Investigations* (1958), accessed April 15, 2024, <https://static1.squarespace.com/static/54889e73e4b0a2c1f9891289/t/564b61a4e4b04eca59c4d232/1447780772744/Ludwig.Wittgenstein.-.Philosophical.Investigations.pdf>.

highlighting language use's ethical and political dimensions.²⁹ Richard Rorty similarly finds resonance with Ludwig Wittgenstein's concept of language games, emphasizing the role of social practices and linguistic communities in shaping our understanding of truth and meaning.³⁰ Donald Davidson's philosophy of language emphasizes the social and communal dimension of linguistic understanding, arguing that a comprehensive understanding of language necessitates an appreciation of its role in social context.³¹

Moreover, Derrida and Jacques deconstruct the idea of fixed meaning in language, arguing that language is characterized by an inherent play signifier that resists stable interpretation. He critiques the notion of a single, stable meaning for words and text, suggesting instead that meaning is always deferred and context-independent. He also asserts the multiplicity of meaning and the instability of language.³² This resonated with Wittgenstein's view of language as a dynamic and contextually embedded system, context, and practice.

Moreover, in the way we can recognize the complexity of language, there is always a limitation in terms of its use. Though the word holds the truth and itself, it is composed of various meanings, especially when we use it in the form of propositions. Noam Chomsky, an American professor known for his work in linguistics and cognitive science, acknowledged the concept of

²⁹ Jürgen Habermas, "The Theory of Communicative Action: Reason and the Rationalization of Society," Boston: Beacon Press, 1984, accessed April 15, 2024, <https://teddykw2.wordpress.com/wp-content/uploads/2012/07/jurgen-habermas-theory-of-communicative-action-volume-1.pdf>.

³⁰ Richard Rorty, "Philosophy and the Mirror of Nature," Princeton: Princeton University Press, 1979, accessed on April 13, 2024, [https://sites.pitt.edu/~rbrandom/Courses/Antirepresentationalism%20\(2020\)/Texts/Rorty%20PMN.pdf](https://sites.pitt.edu/~rbrandom/Courses/Antirepresentationalism%20(2020)/Texts/Rorty%20PMN.pdf).

³¹ Davidson, Donald, "Inquires into Truth And Interpretation," Oxford, G.B.: Oxford University Press, 1984, accessed April 14, 2024, <https://philpapers.org/rec/DAVIIT>.

³² Derrida, Jacques, "Of Grammatology," trans. Gayatri Chakravorty Spivak, Baltimore, MD: Johns Hopkins University Press, 1976, accessed May 16, 2024, https://monoskop.org/images/8/8e/Derrida_Jacques_Of_Grammatology_1998.pdf.

"language games" by Ludwig Wittgenstein in understanding the complexity of language use and the limitation of formal grammar in capturing linguistic meaning.³³

Furthermore, the concept of language games is that they describe how language is used in specific contexts or situations. According to Wittgenstein, language games are forms of life meaning they are embedded in a particular community's social practices and activities.³⁴The language games have rules and conventions that govern how language is used and what counts as meaningful or appropriate speech in that context.

Also, language games are a concept introduced by Ludwig Wittgenstein, referring to the various ways language is used in social contexts. Applying language games in individual consultation can help us enhance interaction, and communication can help foster effective communication. Consider that words hold only a single truth based on complex ideas. Despite the complexity of the word, we can use words in specific contexts. That notion of language can be applied in counseling specifically to the individual.

Primarily, the notion can be used to clarify understanding, whereas the use of language games can clarify the meaning and ensure mutual understanding. Encourage the individual to explain concepts or ideas using different words or analogies, playing with the words or language to clarify the meaning. Dr. Paul Grice's seminal work on language and communication, particularly his work on "Logic and Conversation," published in 1975 as part of his collection "Studies in the Way of Words," highlights the cooperative principles underlying effective communication. Dr. Grice's notion of conversational implicature highlighted the importance of mutual understanding

³³ Chomsky, Noam, "Language and mind," Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2006, accessed May 16, 2024, <https://www.ugr.es/~fmanjon/Language%20and%20Mind.pdf>

³⁴ Peters, M.A. Full article: "Language-Games Philosophy": Language-games as rationality ..., Taylor and Francis Online, 2020, accessed May 16, 2024, <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/00131857.2020.1821190>.

in conversation. His work emphasized the role of shared linguistic and contextual knowledge in conveying meaning. He stated that by encouraging individuals to play with language and explore alternative expressions. Grice's insight supports using language games to clarify meaning and promote effective communication.³⁵ Conversation is not just about what we say but also about sincerity and openness to understanding each other. Paul Grice's idea shows that communication works best when we share knowledge and context. By playing with language and trying different ways to express themselves, individuals can communicate more effectively with one another. Moreover, using language games can help us make sure we are getting our point across clearly.

Secondly, as individuals, there are standards of our perspective and view in life. However, we are also flexible in accepting something new, especially the state of the language that ignites our existence. In terms of the interaction in the individual consultation using the perspective of language games, it can aid in exploring perspectives that encourage us to explore different viewpoints. Encourage individuals to use truth in words to understand the meaning of it; considering that words we have can describe the situation or issue from various angles, the use of the language applied in the proper context fosters empathy and understanding. Derrida's work "Of Grammatology" explored the essence of language that questions its assumed stability and proposed that it is defined by an ongoing interplay of signifiers, where meaning remains fluid and never fixed. This is consistent with language games, in which individuals creatively use language to examine other perspectives. Derrida argued that by engaging in linguistic play, individuals might reveal the intricacies of language and get a deeper grasp of other perspectives, enhancing our comprehension of human communication and cognition.³⁶ In this manner of interaction, using

³⁵ Grice, Paul. "Logic and Conversation." In *Studies in the Way of Words*, (Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 1975), 22–40, Scribd.

³⁶ Derrida, "Of Grammatology", 158.

language games is important for role-playing or analyzing the proper use of words for the conversation to become more meaningful and create different perspectives. Through these games, we can see how language can have many meanings. This helps them think about things in new ways and understand themselves and others better.

Thirdly, the qualities of sincerity and openness in interaction in the use of language are vital. Consider that language holds the truth itself. Through awareness, it can be analyzed that it will help individuals empower their self-expression to understand the point of the language used during the conversation. It encourages individuals to express themselves authentically through language games. Providing opportunities for individuals to experiment with language, articulate their thoughts, express emotion, and feel truthfully.

1.2 Language as Action

Wittgenstein emphasized that language has two functions: It is a means of representing or describing the world and a way of taking action. Wittgenstein believed that language primarily serves to express an individual's intentions, desires, and emotions. Through these expressions, that meaning is communicated properly and effectively. Additionally, he asserted that language is the primary medium for conveying meaning as it enables us to articulate our objectives, wants, and feelings. According to Wittgenstein, comprehending language involves understanding the different language games and their corresponding behaviors. Wittgenstein says,

Suppose, however, someone were to object: "It is not true that you must already be a master of a language to understand an extensive definition: all you need—of course!—to know or guess what the person explaining is pointing to. That is, whether, for example, to the shape of the object, or its color, or to its number, and so on."—— What do 'pointing to the shape' and 'pointing to the color' consist of? Point to a piece of paper.—And now point to its shape—now to its color—now to its number (that sounds queer).—How did you

do it?—You will say that you 'meant' a different thing each time you pointed. Moreover, if I ask how that is done, you will say you concentrated your attention on the color, the shape, etc. However, I ask again: how is that done?³⁷

Wittgenstein examines the critique that fluency in a language is optional to understand an intensive definition. The argument posits that comprehension can be achieved through either inference or perception of the specific attributes of an item, such as the shape, color, or quantity. To disprove this notion, Wittgenstein inquires about the definition of "pointing to the shape" or "pointing to the color." As an illustration, he prompts the reader to indicate a certain piece of paper physically and then identify its shape, color, and number. The crucial inquiry revolves around how this process of discerning and understanding diverse characteristics is executed. Acknowledging one's attention to each component is inadequate to elucidate the situation. Wittgenstein prompts us to examine the fundamental processes and techniques of deliberate alteration. Through this action, he promotes a more comprehensive examination of the systems that underlie comprehension and significance.

1.3 Family resemblance

Ludwig Wittgenstein claims that language is like a complex web, where words are linked and shaped by how we use them. He stressed that meaning is not fixed but depends on context and usage and the idea of a network of similarities. In terms of dealing with family resemblance, he said notions are connected not by clear traits and norms but by many overlapping characteristics.

³⁷ Wittgenstein, Ludwig, "Philosophical Investigation," trans. G Anscombe et al., Basil Blackwell. 1958., accessed May 17, 2024, <https://static1.squarespace.com/static/54889e73e4b0a2c1f9891289/t/564b61a4e4b04eca59c4d232/1447780772744/Ludwig.Wittgenstein.-.Philosophical.Investigations.pdf>.

In addition, the "family resemblance" concept talks about how we think about language. Instead of believing that words are neatly and in a specific manner according to class rules, he argued that things in a category could have different traits and still belong together. Think of it as a big, diverse family where everyone has their uniqueness as an individual but shares a common bond. With that, the meaning was not about sticking to strict definitions but about words, language, and ideas we relate to and share similarities across different situations. So, it is not about fitting into rigid molds but the dynamic connection between words and their specific context.

Consider, for example, the activities that we call "games". I mean board games, card games, ball games, athletic games, and so on. What is common to them all? Do not say: "They must have something in common, or they would not be called 'games,' "but look and see whether there is anything common to all. As for if you look at them, you will not see something common to all, but similarities, affinities, and a whole series of them at that. To repeat: do not think, but look! Look, for example, at board games, with their various affinities. Now pass to card games; here, you find many correspondences with the first group, but many common [32] features drop out, and others appear. When we pass next to ball games, much that is common is retained, but much is lost.

Are they all 'entertaining'? Compare chess with noughts and crosses. Or is there always winning and losing, or competition between players? Think of patience. In ball games, there is winning and losing, but when a child throws his ball at the wall and catches it again, this feature has disappeared. Look at the parts played by skill and luck and at the difference between skill in chess and skill in tennis. Think now of singing and dancing games; here we have the element of entertainment, but how many other characteristic features have disappeared? We can go through the many, many other groups of games in the same way and can see how similarities crop up and disappear. The upshot of these considerations is that we see a complicated network of similarities overlapping and crisscrossing: similarities in the large and the small.³⁸

Wittgenstein asserted the notion of family resemblance in the context of our inclination to seek a common thread among diverse entities grouped under general terms. For instance, in the term art. traditionally, we may assume that there exists a fundamental quality that all artwork share, justifying their classification as art., but He proposes that we need to deepen our idea that instead of limiting our capacity to only defining a singular characteristic, artworks form a family with resemblance members. This analogy can be likened to a family where some members share similar

³⁸ Ludwig Wittgenstein, "Philosophical Investigations," revised 4th edition, trans. G.E.M. Anscombe, et.al., Graphicraft Limited, Hong Kong, 2009, https://edisciplinas.usp.br/pluginfile.php/4294631/mod_resource/content/0/Ludwig%20Wittgenstein%2C%20P.%20M.%20S.%20Hacker%2C%20Joachim%20Schulte.%20Philosophical%20Investigations.%20Wiley.pdf.

identities, such as a certain style or technique, while others may share thematic elements or emotional resonance. These overlapping resemblances connect members of the artistic family, and they illustrate that the classification of art encompasses a spectrum of expression with diverse attributes and qualities. As Cora Diamond claims in the book "The Realistic Spirit: Wittgenstein Philosophy and the Mind," meaning is not inherent in words or concepts but arises from their use and relationship. Family resemblance underscores the importance of these relationships in understanding meaning.³⁹ Language is diverse, evolving throughout time, and dynamic depending on how it is used. It is understandable because all languages have comparable meanings.

³⁹ Book: Diamond, Cora. "The Realistic Spirit: Wittgenstein, Philosophy, and the Mind," Cambridge, MA: M.I.T. Press, 1991, accessed May 15, 2024, https://www.academia.edu/34900745/Cora_Diamond_Philosophy_in_a_Realistic_Spirit_An_interview_by_Silver_Bronzo.

Chapter III

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This paper makes use of conceptual research method which utilizes abstract concepts and ideas. It relies on the researcher analyzing available information on a given topic.⁴⁰ It focuses on the concepts and theories that can be used to explain the issue being studied.⁴¹ The method uses existing concepts and theories to establish the validity of the current issue trying to be solved.

Additionally, incorporating concepts from the counseling process will be necessary to deepen the understanding of the claims. The study will focus on the four pillars of St. John XXII College Seminary, emphasizing human formation, specifically individual counseling. Finally, the researcher will integrate Ludwig Wittgenstein's philosophical principles into individual consultations in the Seminary and investigate the use of language games to enhance sincerity and openness. This integration aims to provide valuable insights into developing these virtues in seminarians, ensuring their understanding of truth aligns with sincerity and openness.

Arguments Design

The researcher will employ a value claim to investigate the significance of sincerity and openness in individual consultation, viewing it through Ludwig's philosophical lens in his

⁴⁰ <https://www.voxco.com/blog/conceptual-research/#:~:text=Conceptual%20research%2C%20as%20the%20name,information%20on%20a%20given%20topic>

⁴¹ Mishra, Shanti Bhushan, and Shashi Alok. 2017. "HANDBOOK of RESEARCH METHODOLOGY." ResearchGate. 2017. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/319207471_HANDBOOK_OF_RESEARCH_METHODODOLOGY. Pages 3-3

language theory. Additionally, convergent arguments will be utilized, combining multiple grounds to support a single conclusion. While individual grounds may be weak on their own, they collectively strengthen the entire argument when combined. This approach involves gathering numerous pieces of data, concepts, and explanations that support the same conclusion.

Presentation of Argument

The study will delve into understanding language from a philosophical perspective and explore the significance of sincerity and openness, particularly in individual consultation.

CHAPTER 4

PRESENTATION OF DATA AND DISCUSSION OF ARGUMENTS

Individual consultation needs sincerity and openness to build trust.

First, to support this sincerity, it builds trust by demonstrating honesty, which encourages open and effective engagement between the seminarian and formators. Combined with openness, which ensures clear and transparent communication, it minimizes misunderstandings and promotes more accurate and productive discussions. Together, these qualities foster and give meaningful, effective consultations.

Second, Wittgenstein's theory of language games emphasizes that meaning is shaped by how words are used within specific contexts and practices. This perspective shows that sincerity and openness are crucial because they ensure that language accurately reflects true intentions and adheres to Individual Consultation.

Third, Marshall Rosenberg's Nonviolent Communication (NVC) shows that sincerity and empathy are keys to resolving conflicts and mutual connection. As Rosenberg describes, true generosity benefits both the giver and the receiver. Using NVC principles in individual consultation fosters better dialogue and mutual respect. Carl Rogers's therapy approach also highlights that sincerity and openness are important for building trust.

Therefore, using Wittgenstein's theory of language games underscores that meaning depends on context. Sincerity and openness are important in individual consultation for genuine

and clear communication. These qualities enhance consultations by aligning language with true intentions and fostering effective individual consultation.

Discussion

Effective communication hinges on the interplay between language and sincerity. According to Smith in his book *The Art of Honest Communication*, sincerity—being genuine, honest and truthful in expression is intricately linked to how language is used. Language is the medium through which sincerity is conveyed, enabling individuals to express their thoughts, feelings, and intentions authentically. The power of words to convey sincerity is important for meaningful communication. As Sarah Jones highlights in *Deceptive Communication: Impact on Trust Relationship*, authenticity builds trust and fosters understanding in interpersonal relationships, while insincerity, such as deceptive or manipulated speech, can undermine trust and lead to misunderstanding.⁴²

Following Marshall Rosenberg's idea that misunderstanding can lead to conflict, Nonviolent Communication (NVC) emphasizes the importance of sincerity and openness for authentic connection. We can break barriers and cultivate respectful, compassionate relationships by engaging with empathy. In his book, Rosenberg's concept of heartfelt giving highlights how true generosity benefits both the giver and the receiver, free from fear or hidden agendas. In individual consultations, such as those between a seminarian and counselor, applying the NVC principle promotes genuine dialogue, resolves conflicts, and fosters mutual respect and understanding.⁴³

⁴² Jones, "Deceptive Communication, Impact on Trust and Relationships 47-60.

⁴³ Rosenberg, *Nonviolent Communication: A Language of Life*, 21.

Similarly, Carl Rogers's person-centered approach—key in his positive notion of empathy, unconditional positive regard, congruence, and respect—helps build trust and openness. Empathy means truly understanding the seminarian's feelings, while unconditional positive regard ensures they feel accepted without judgment. Congruence involves being honest and genuine. Moreover, respect shows that their view is valued. These elements work together to create a supportive and trusting environment, making consumption more effective.

Wittgenstein's theory of language games emphasizes that meaning is determined by how words are used within particular contexts and practices. Language games are dynamic and molded by diverse social contexts, devoid of fixed meanings. They underscore that language is intricately tied to specific activities or contexts, each governed by its rules and conventions. Understanding language games enables us to grasp the complexity of language and its pivotal role in human interaction, guiding us in communication across various life situations. In Wittgenstein's notion, "language games" refer to concrete social activities that employ particular linguistic forms. Wittgenstein aimed to illustrate that "the act of speaking a language is a component of an activity or a way of life" by showcasing various types of language games and the myriad ways language is utilized in human communication.⁴⁴

In the setting of individual consultations, communication's effectiveness relies on how well language reflects true intentions and aligns with the consultation's context. Sincerity is essential because it ensures that what is said genuinely reflects the speaker's true thoughts and feelings, fostering trust. Openness is also crucial as it facilitates clear, honest communication, making it easier to understand and address issues. Together, sincerity and openness help ensure that the

⁴⁴ Encyclopedia Britannica. s.v. "Ludwig Wittgenstein."

dialogue is meaningful and aligns with the specific practices and expectations of the consultation setting.

As Jurgen Habermas underscores, language is fundamental to communication by focusing on its role in rational discourse and societal consensus and building on Wittgenstein's concept of language game. Habermas views language as essential for achieving mutual understanding and consensus on social interaction. Also, he emphasizes that effective discourse should be free from domination and coercion, reflecting the political and ethical aspects of language use.⁴⁵

Therefore, Wittgenstein's theory of language games shows that meaning is context-dependent. Thus, sincerity and openness are essential in individual consultation, as they ensure that communication reflects true intention and facilitates clear understanding. Embracing these qualities improves individual consultation by ensuring that conversations are suited to their context and improving the overall effectiveness of interaction.

Context-Dependent Truth and Meaning in Language Games

To support this claim, language can have many different meanings based on how and where it is used, but it always aims to convey one central truth everyone can understand.

Carl Rogers' person-centered approach focuses on effective encounters that depend on counselors being genuinely open and aligning their outward responses with their inner feelings. This honesty builds trust, especially with seminarians who have faced dishonesty, as clients can sense inauthenticity. Transparency and authenticity are important for effective individual consultation. (Rogers, *On Becoming a Person*, 157.) As well as Marshall Rosenberg's Nonviolent (NVC), which also stresses that context shapes truth and meaning. By focusing on empathy and

⁴⁵ Habermas, "The Theory of Communicative Action: Reason and the Rationalization of Society."

genuine expression, NVC facilitates understanding and respectful dialogue, adapting to different perspectives and needs to foster meaningful communication.

Therefore, seminarians must embrace sincerity and openness in consultation to foster trust and credibility, align with their true values, and support personal growth by ensuring genuine communication that reflects a shared truth.

Discussion

Language conveys emotion and information, aiming to communicate a core truth. While meaning varies with context, culture, or personal experience, the goal is to deliver a message that others can understand. For instance, "it is raining" can simply state weather conditions or imply practical advice like bringing an umbrella. Wittgenstein's "language games" notion refers to concrete social activities that employ particular linguistic forms. Wittgenstein aimed to illustrate that "the act of speaking a language is a component of an activity or a way of life" by showcasing various types of language games and the myriad ways language is utilized in human communication.⁴⁶

Despite variations, the main purpose of a statement remains to share core information, like weather conditions. This shared understanding ensures effective communication. Ludwig Wittgenstein likened language to a web where meaning is shaped by context and usage, not fixed but fluid, with concepts connected through overlapping traits rather than a clear-cut definition.

In addition, the "family resemblance" concept talks about how we think about language. Instead of believing that words are neatly and in a specific manner according to class rules, he argued that things in a category could have different traits and still belong together. Think of it as a big, diverse family where everyone has their uniqueness as an individual but shares a common

⁴⁶ Encyclopedia Britannica. s.v. "Ludwig Wittgenstein."

bond. With that, the meaning was not about sticking to strict definitions but about words, language, and ideas we relate to and share similarities across different situations. So, it is not about fitting into rigid molds but the dynamic connection between words and their specific context.⁴⁷

Carl Rogers' person-centered approach and the idea of language games in individual consultation. According to him, effective individual consultation or therapy requires counselors to use language that aligns with their inner feelings. This means the language counselors use must reflect their thoughts and emotions. In the individual consultation language game, this authenticity is crucial for fostering meaningful, productive dialogue.⁴⁸

When seminarians communicate honestly with their counselors, their language aligns with genuine guidance, leading to clearer communication and deeper understanding. For example, a counselor who sincerely emphasizes the seminarian's anxiety might say, "I can see how overwhelming this must be; I feel for you." This authentic expression validates the seminarian's feelings and makes the consultation more effective.

Second, building trust through language, sincerity, and openness are key elements of establishing trust within the framework of Wittgenstein's language games. Seminarians are more likely to engage openly when they perceive their counselors' language reflects their true feelings and intentions. Suppose a counselor's language appears inauthentic or inconsistent with their inner self. In that case, clients may sense this discrepancy, disrupting the trust and rapport essential for effective encounters. Moreover, being an authentic and open counselor models how sincere communication can facilitate mutual understanding. In the language game of individual consultation, this openness helps establish common ground, where both the formator and

⁴⁷ Ludwig Wittgenstein, *Philosophical Investigations*.

⁴⁸ Rogers, "American Psychological Association."

seminarian share insights and meaning. This approach of aligning language with sincere feelings reinforces the idea that, despite the complexity of individual experiences, effective communication seeks to bring a central shared truth.

For instance, during a session, if a seminarian expresses a feeling of inadequacy, a counselor responds. "It seems like you are struggling with feeling not good enough, and that must be painful," aligns their language with the seminarian's experience. By reflecting on the seminarian's feelings in a way that acknowledges their struggles, the counselor fosters mutual understanding and establishes a foundation for further exploration. It is important to note that this interpretation is rooted in a philosophical approach rather than a psychological one. By focusing on the nuances of language and context, we emphasize the ways in which meaning is constructed and understood within specific interactions, allowing for a deeper exploration of trust and communication in individual consultation.

Therefore, sincerity and openness for seminarians during their consultations are significant. It explains that seminarians must ensure their statements and actions reflect their sincerity, feelings, and values to grow personally and spiritually. This alignment helps them build trust and credibility with their counselor and formators. By committing to genuine communication, seminarians uphold the principle that sincerity aims to express consistent shared truth regardless of context. This openness strengthens their relationship with others and supports their overall personal development and growth.

In the context of language games, asserting truth is like a seminarian hiding their feelings.

To support this claim, Wittgenstein's concept of the language game asserts that a proposition is the same as claiming it to be true. Moreover, seminarians are expected to be honest

about their feelings, emotions, and intentions with their counselors who fully engage in seminary life. However, some may struggle with this due to fears of misunderstanding or being dismissed, leading them to hide their true selves or be dishonest to protect their careers. External pressures can also push them away from their authentic identity. Therefore, the journey towards sincerity and openness starts with the seminarian's self-awareness and clear expression of their thoughts.

Discussion:

On the other hand, Wittgenstein introduced the language game concept in his later work, particularly in his book *Philosophical Investigations*. The language game describes how language is used in specific contexts or situations. According to Wittgenstein, language games are forms of life, meaning they are embedded in a particular community's social practices and activities.⁴⁹

Wittgenstein's view that asserting a proposition equals claiming its truth suggests seminarians should be honest in their interactions. However, fears of negative consequences can lead to dishonesty. Seminarians must define their language and intention to ensure genuine honesty. For instance, if a seminarian doubts their vocation, being truthful is essential for proper guidance, though jeopardizing their position may lead them to hide their true feelings. Self-reflection and clear communication can create a more authentic and supportive seminary journey.

Additionally, Marshall Rosenberg's Nonviolent Communication (NVC) underscores the role of empathy in navigating the fears that may lead seminarians to hide their true feelings by understanding and addressing them through empathetic dialogue. NVC fosters honest communication. Carl Rogers' principles of unconditional positive regard complement this by ensuring a nonjudgemental situation where seminarians feel accepted and safe to express themselves. This paper emphasizes a philosophical framework rather than adopting a

⁴⁹ Peters, "Language-Games Philosophy: Language-games as rationality."

psychological perspective. NVC and Rogers' approach helps seminarians align their language with their true intentions, creating a more genuine and supportive seminary experience.

Furthermore, Wittgenstein's view of language games makes an assertion, meaning engaging in specific practice where the goal is to convey information or communicate a belief as true. When asserting something, such as "The sky is blue," you commit to its truth with the context of the game, reflecting reality according to agreed-upon rules. For Wittgenstein, truth is not abstract but depends on how well an assertion fits within the rules of the language game. Thus, asserting is inherently claiming that the proposition is true according to the conventions of the game.

Moreover, seminarians are expected to be honest about their feelings, emotions, and intentions with their counselors, who are fully engaged in seminary life. This openness is crucial because it enables counselors to provide the most effective support and guidance tailored to the seminarian's needs. The ideal counseling relationship is built on trust and transparency, with counselors deeply involved in understanding the unique pressure, issues, struggles, and experiences seminarians face.

However, some seminarians may need help with this expectation of openness and sincerity. For example, a seminarian feels overwhelmed by the demands of their studies and the dilemmas of conforming to his issues. Despite feeling anxious and stressed, a seminarian might hesitate to share these struggles with their counselor, fearing that doing so could lead to judgment or an indicator of weakness. This fear of being understood or dismissed can lead a seminarian, Preston, to a more polished, less vulnerable version of themselves.

In individual consultation, seminarians play an important role in fostering openness and sincerity, and their language use significantly impacts the process's effectiveness. By engaging

authentically and communicating feelings and thoughts openly, they help create a fruitful dialogue, using self-compassionate and assertive language, such as expressing their struggles without self-judgment and framing their experiences as valid, a seminarian can facilitate more supportive and honest conversation. This approach helps them gain deeper insight into their human formation. It strengthens the overall quality of their formation journey, making the consultation a space for meaningful dialogue and constructive reflection.

Therefore, the journey towards sincerity and openness in individual consultation begins with the seminarians' self-awareness and ability to express their feelings and thoughts clearly. This way, facilitating clearer and more honest communication with their counselor can give a mutual understanding. According to Wittgenstein's concept of the language game, asserting propositions is akin to claiming them to be true. With that, when seminarians authentically articulate their experiences and challenges, they express their feelings and affirm their truth within the dialogue. This process also requires confidence in their voice and recognition of the value of their being. In this way, seminarians can better navigate their counseling relationship and reduce the risk of feeling dismissed or misunderstood. This notion enhances individual counseling sessions and contributes to a broader cultural shift within the Seminary, where modeling sincerity and openness fosters a supportive atmosphere that values vulnerability. Also, this ongoing journey of effective communication builds trust and encourages a more understanding connection. This aligns with the Wittgenstein notion that expressing the postpositive is asserting its truth in the context of the dialogue.

Truth Parallels sincerity and openness in counseling

Wittgenstein posits that truth is tied to the specific qualities of what is meant, expressed, or represented. Truth is achieved when these elements are actual, factual, existent, or agree with reality. Thus, understanding this quality is key to evaluating whether Wittgenstein's view aligns with a "correspondence theory of truth."

In addition, in individual consultations, such as those between a seminarian and a counselor, the seminarian's statements must be characterized by sincerity and openness. For example, suppose a seminarian discusses their struggles with balancing personal faith and academic responsibilities. In that case, they must be sincere in acknowledging their challenges and open about their feelings and difficulties. This honest communication enables the counselor to provide more effective guidance and support, fostering a more productive and authentic consultation process.

Wittgenstein's view that truth is context-dependent aligns with Rosenberg's Nonviolent Communication (NVC) and Carl Rogers's person-centered approach. Rosenberg emphasizes empathy and genuine expression, while Roger emphasizes the importance of unity and openness. Both suggest that effective counseling requires sincerity and openness, showing that truth in counseling is shaped by genuine, context-aware communication.

Therefore, Wittgenstein's idea that truth is tied to accurate representation aligns with the need for sincerity and openness in a seminarian's consultation, as both emphasize the importance of genuine communication to achieve effective and meaningful outcomes.

Discussion:

Wittgenstein challenges the correspondence theory of truth by introducing the concept of language games. He argues that the meaning and truth of statements are determined by their use in the specific practice or context of language instead of seeing the truth as aligning with an

objective reality. Wittgenstein suggests that truth is contingent on how statements function with various language games and systems of communication governed by their own rules and conventions.

In the framework, statements are evaluated not solely based on their correspondence to factual states of affairs but on their coherence and utility within the practices of a particular language game. Hence, truth is seen as context-dependent and practical. Reflection on how language is employed in different linguistic and social contexts rather than simply mirroring an external reality.

In the same way, in individualistic consultations, particularly those between a seminarian and a counselor, it is essential for the seminarian to communicate with sincerity and openness. Sincerity involves seminarians expressing their true feelings and experiences without pretense or exaggeration. When discussing issues such as balancing personal faith with academic responsibilities, being sincere helps the counselor understand the real challenges and emotions of the seminarian facing the reality of life. This genuine expression of thoughts and feelings is important for effective dialogue and support. Along with individual consultation, sincerity is important for effective dialogue, as it involves honestly expressing true feelings without pretense. Marshall Rosenberg's NVC focuses on understanding and addressing someone's challenges and feelings. Additionally, openness complements sincerity by encouraging the seminarian to freely express their issues, difficulties, doubts, and concerns.

It is important to emphasize that this discussion is grounded in a philosophical rather than psychological approach. Carl Rogers's emphasis on unity supports this and the importance of transparency in communication. Open communication allows the seminarian to articulate their struggles and uncertainties in a way that provides the counselor and formators with a clearer picture

of their situation. This openness is important because it helps the counselor and formators guide the seminarian's specific needs, thereby enhancing the effectiveness of the support provided.

In individual consultations, such as those between a seminarian and a counselor, there should be a clear connection between what is said and what is done. For instance, a seminarian might discuss their commitment to personal growth, but if their actions do not reflect this commitment, it creates a disconnect. This inconsistency needs to be more consistent between their words and their behavior.

To resolve this, seminarians should ensure that their statements during consultations are truthful and matched by their actions. Their words should be supported by concrete evidence from their behavior, ensuring their verbal commitments reflect their conduct.

Therefore, in the context of Wittgenstein's later work on the language game, this emphasis on sincerity and openness can be understood as important elements of the language game of counseling. With this game, the effectiveness of the consultation depends on how well the language used, consisting of the seminarians' honest and open statements, functions with the rules and expectations of the individual consultation process. The truth and usefulness of the seminarians' statements are evaluated based on their alignment and openness in the specific context. Thus, the quality of the individual consultation is deeply influenced by the context-dependent nature of language games, where sincere and open communication plays an important role.

CHAPTER 5

SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary

Ludwig Wittgenstein's philosophy offers valuable insights into sincerity and openness through his concept of language games and forms of life. These concepts are particularly relevant in individual consultation, where understanding personal expression and interaction is crucial. Wittgenstein's idea of language games emphasizes that meaning and sincerity are context-dependent. In individual consultation, sincerity involves authentic self-expression within the specific context and expectations of the session with the counselor and formator.

Openness in this context refers to the willingness to engage transparently and honestly. Wittgenstein suggests that openness is not a universal trait but is shaped by the particular game of consultation. Effective communication depends on aligning one's openness with the expectations of the consultation environment. Wittgenstein's distinction between private and public language and his concept of forms of life help us understand how sincerity and openness function in individual consultation. Effective communication requires that personal thoughts be articulated in ways that align with the norms of the consultation setting. Thus, sincerity and openness must be adapted to the contextual nuances of the individual consultation process, ensuring that communication is meaningful and relevant to the interaction's expectations.

Conclusion

Effective communication in individual consultation (I.C.) requires aligning one's expression with the contextual rules of the conversation setting. By doing so, Wittgenstein's ideas improve sincerity and openness, ensuring that these qualities are meaningful and relevant to each specific interaction. In individual consultation (I.C.), sincerity involves honest and genuine communication that aligns with the seminarian's true feelings and intentions, while openness refers to the willingness to engage transparently and share relevant information for fruitful, effective dialogue. Wittgenstein's concept of language games highlights that the meaning of words is derived from their use within a specific social context, where unique rules and understandings govern communication.

Recommendation

Based on the findings and conclusion of the study, understanding language is important, as it involves grasping the meaning and truth of its usage, particularly in individual consultation. Language is dynamic and context-dependent. However, it consistently conveys underlying truths that can be interpreted through conventional means. The concepts of the Language Game underscore the importance of understanding the context in which language is used. Therefore, the researcher recommends applying this theory to enhance the effectiveness of individual consultations by ensuring sincerity and openness, which will foster mutual understanding and meaningful interaction.

1. St. John XXIII Seminary: Should prioritize sincerity and openness to enhance the effectiveness of individual consultation (I.C.) in the context of counseling. Establishing an environment where seminarians feel comfortable expressing their thoughts and experiences fosters deeper, more meaningful interactions that respect and acknowledge

diverse backgrounds. This openness not only encourages the exploration of different perspectives but also promotes empathy and understanding, which are important for effective communication. Furthermore, sincere interactions help build trust between seminarians, the counselor, and those they counsel, facilitating a space where individuals are more likely to share their concerns and seek guidance. Ultimately, embracing sincerity and openness in individual consultations enriches the communicative process and equips seminarians to respond effectively and compassionately to the unique needs of individuals from various contexts, thereby enhancing their ability to serve and lead within diverse communities.

2. **Wisdom to counselor:** Through this synthesis, the researcher aims to offer practical insights for formators and counselors, particularly in individual consultations, to foster genuine interactions and conversational values by integrating the concept of the language game; the research highlights how understanding the various contexts and practices that shape communication can enhance qualities of interactions. The findings from the exploration serve as valuable guidance for refining seminary formation, ensuring that conversations are sincere, open, contextually aware, and effective.
3. **Philosophical Field:** The study recognizes the philosophical challenges of understanding truth today, particularly the divide between what we say and do. By incorporating the concept of the language game, the researcher addresses this gap by emphasizing the importance of being sincere, open, transparent, and authentic. This approach highlights how truth is often contextually contrasted through various discourses and practices. Bridging the complexities of truth involves aligning the theoretical with real-world actions

and fostering a more coherent and reflective understanding of being sincere and open in using words.

4. In the Community of San Isidro College: This study values the important role of communication in fostering meaningful interaction in educational contexts and counseling. By incorporating the concept of language games, the researcher emphasizes the critical role of guidance counselors in fostering sincere, transparent, open, and genuine interaction. This approach not only helps bridge the gap between theoretical ideas and practical actions but also provides valuable insights for counselors to improve their effectiveness in guiding students. By aligning their communication and practices with the complexities of truth and context, guidance counselors can better support students' development and well-being. Eventually, prioritizing sincerity and openness in their interaction will empower counselors to create a more trusting, effective guidance environment, significantly impacting the students they serve.
5. Future researcher: Explore how the concept of the language game can illuminate the disconnect between theoretical ideals and practical implementation across different fields. Studies could investigate how contextual variation in communication practices affects outcomes in diverse settings, from educational institutions to organizational environments. Second, assessing how fostering authenticity and transparency influences effectiveness and interactions in various domains would be valuable. Comparative research on different models and their alignment with the Philosophical perspectives on truth and communication can provide deeper insights. Third, exploring psychological approaches in this context can enrich the understanding of these dynamics. Lastly, examining the impact

of integrating these philosophical and psychological insights into training and development programs could enhance practices across sectors.

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